

Effectiveness of Implant Design On Implant Stability

Ayesha Indira Gupta¹
Reshu Sanan²
Bhupender Yadav³
Omkar Shetty⁴

Post Graduate Student¹
Department of Prosthodontics, Crown & Bridge
and Oral Implantology
S.G.T. Dental College, Hospital and Research Institute
Gurugram, Haryana

Professor²
Department of Prosthodontics, Crown & Bridge
and Oral Implantology
S.G.T. Dental College, Hospital and Research Institute
Gurugram, Haryana

Professor and Head³
Department of Prosthodontics, Crown & Bridge
and Oral Implantology
S.G.T. Dental College, Hospital and Research Institute
Gurugram, Haryana

Professor and Dean⁴
Department of Prosthodontics, Crown & Bridge
and Oral Implantology
S.G.T. Dental College, Hospital and Research Institute
Gurugram, Haryana

Submitted 01 October 2025
Accepted 08 October 2025
Published xx xxx xxxx

<p>Access this Article Online Website: www.healtalk.in DOI</p>	<p>Quick Response Code</p>
---	----------------------------

Abstract

With the advent of implants, other options of rehabilitation such as removable dentures and crowns have taken a backseat. Implants are placed after meticulous planning and after placement there are specific criteria that can predict and determine their success. At present the implant survival rate ranges from 90 – 95 percent over a 10 year observation period. Implant survival depends upon implant stability both at the time of placement and as the treatment progresses. Implant stability is of two types, primary and secondary and there are various factors that influence implant stability. Recently, a wide array of researches has been conducted on factors improving implant stability. The factors influencing implant stability include implant design, implant surface topography, bone quality, and patient-related factors. Implant design has gained particular relevance especially because the intricacies in implant design are increasing over the years. The role of implant design on implant stability has been explored. Various aspects of implant design which includes its macro and micro geometry play their respective parts in optimizing implant stability. With the available information, the present review aims to discuss the implant design factors associated with implant stability.

Keywords: Implant stability, implant design, thread design, macrogeometry, microgeometry .

Introduction

Implants in dentistry are becoming the more sought after treatment option. In an edentulous space, an implant can be placed without using the support of abutment teeth. This makes implant therapy a conservative treatment option unlike fixed partial dentures wherein adjacent teeth need to be prepared. It is also better to use an implant compared to other removable treatment options because removable prosthesis require constant attention and lack the natural simulation created by an implant. Prior to the placement of the implant various factors are evaluated. A thorough understanding of all the factors involved in the treatment planning of implants is of utmost importance. According to Misch¹, there are eight factors to be considered in the treatment planning of an implant. They include, prosthesis design, patient force factors, bone density in the edentulous sites, key implant positions, implant number, implant size, available bone in the edentulous sites and implant design.¹ All these factors influence one another and vary from case to case. Historically, the implant number and position took precedence over the prosthesis design. However, our main goal is to provide rehabilitation of missing teeth; in other words the patient is missing teeth and not implants. The treatment

planning should take place in retrograde where the rehabilitating prosthesis dictates the implant position and number.² The ideal treatment plan is established while considering the number and position of missing teeth and then modified based on patient force factors.³ The forces exerted onto the prosthesis depend upon parafunctional habits, masticatory dynamics, opposing dentition, crown height space and arch position.⁴ The next most important criteria is bone density; bone density varies according to the edentulous site. Bone density can provide valuable input to the treatment plan; for example weaker bone density requires wider implants. Overall, the poorer the bone density the greater the implant support required.

The last of the factors mentioned include implant design which will be the highlight of this article. Implants can be broadly divided into three parts; the crest module, the body and the apex. The crest module receives the abutment in the latter stages of treatment. Earlier, the crest module formed the trans-

How to Cite This Article : Gupta et al. -

osseal portion of the implant; however with the introduction of subcrestal implants the whole of the implant, including the crest module lies primarily within bone. The crest module may be optimized to increase bone implant contact, however that function is mainly taken care of by the body of the implant.⁵ The body of the implant lies in direct contact with the bone. This bone implant contact (BIC) is essential for the stability of the implant. By virtue of this contact the implant derives stability. The crest module plays a minor role in stabilizing the implant within the bone. It houses the anti rotation components required to attach the abutment onto the implant. The body of the implant, referred to as 'root form endosteal implants', is of three types; cylindrical type, screw type and a combination of both. Cylinder implants can be parallel walled or tapered; they are generally pushed or tapped into the prepared bone site. Due to the lack of threads within this design they depend upon the surface condition for retention. Screw root form implants on the other hand derive their retention from threads mainly; additionally they may also have surface treatments to enhance retention. Thread shape, thread pitch, helix angle of the thread and other features associated with the threads make the screw root form implants more complex and better for implant stability.⁵ Several important design factors can affect implant stability including implant diameter, implant length, implant thread design, implant surface roughness, and implant shape.⁷ All of these features of an implant should be optimized in order to provide maximum bone implant contact which will lead to good implant stability. A thorough understanding of implant design including its macro and microgeometry is important to understand their effect on primary and secondary stability. Good implant stability is a fixed determinant for the success of an implant. The two types of stability that can be achieved are primary and secondary stability. Primary stability refers to the mechanical seating of the implant. The engagement of the implant with the bone provides stability to the implant. The aim is to provide maximum stability with minimum movement at the bone implant interface.⁸ Secondary stability, on the other hand, comes after primary stability and primarily refers to the stability achieved between bone and implant after the process of osseointegration has taken place. This is also referred to as biological stability because the new bone is now integrated to the implant surface.⁹ Primary and secondary stability are positively correlated with each other. According to literature, if the micro motion is above the range of 50 – 150 microns during the measurement of primary stability, the secondary stability does not properly take place. This is because micro motion between bone and implant above this range will result in fibrous encapsulation as opposed to osseointegration.¹⁰

With the introduction of immediate placement and immediate loading of implants the stability of implants has become an even more crucial factor. The implant design has to be optimized in such scenarios as well to give a better stability. Implant placement can be divided into immediate, early and delayed. Immediate implant placement as the name suggests, is the immediate placement of an implant into the extraction socket after the extraction of the tooth. Early placement is 2–4 week delayed implantation after extraction and allowing soft tissue healing. Delayed approach is the conventional method which describes implantation after 4–6 months of waiting for complete healing time.¹¹ Right after the placement of an implant the bone implant contact creates primary stability in all three cases. However, immediate implant placement poses the maximum challenge owing to the compromised condition

of the hard and soft tissues. Just like implant placement, implant loading can also be classified into immediate, early and delayed (or conventional).¹² Loading refers to the prosthetic rehabilitation of the implant by virtue of which the implant is brought into function. Since occlusal forces come into play after loading, loading creates stresses at the bone implant interface. This makes implant stability even more important. The stability of the implant dictates loading protocols. If immediate loading is being considered then primary stability plays and even greater role; this is because the load distribution will be immediate and during the period when primary stability dominates (upto 4weeks). Immediate implant loading will depend upon primary stability of the implant where as delayed loading will depend upon the secondary stability as it will occur after the new bone formation has already taken place.

The present review aims to discuss implant design features involved in stability. It also gives us idea of proper selection of implant design in scenarios such as immediate placement and immediate loading where implant stability plays an even more important role.

Implant Design Considerations

Implant Macrogeometry

The Crest Module

The crest module serves as the transition zone between the implant body and the prosthesis. The crest module might extend into the soft tissue zone in which case it is referred to as transosteal. In case the total implant including the crest module is submerged into the bone it may be referred to as sub crestal. The crest module can further be reviewed under shape, size and surface.¹³

Shape of the Crest Module

The shape of the crest module determines the stresses created between the bone and the implant at the crest of the bone. The stresses come into play when the implant is loaded. Regardless of the loading protocol used these stresses may affect the primary and/or secondary stability of the implant.¹³ As a general rule shear stresses are minimized while compressive stresses are preferred because bone is strongest when loaded in compression, 30% weaker to tensile loads, and 65% weaker to shear loads. Misch and Bidez¹⁴ claimed that when compared to parallel walled implants, crest modules designed at 20 degree angulations provide the benefit of compressive and tensile components; a surface texture may also be added.¹⁴ Wan-Ling Shen et al.¹⁵ compared the three most common shapes of crest module: straight, divergent and convergent. According to his findings the divergent collar design produced least stress and strain followed by the straight type and the convergent one.¹⁵ The reason for this is that the divergent collar design provides the maximum surface area of bone implant contact.

Size of the Crest Module

As demonstrated by a finite element analysis by Cynthia et al¹⁶, increasing the crestal diameter led to a decrease in strain at the crestal region by 3.5.¹⁶ The crest module diameter is kept larger than the outer diameter of the body of the implant to provide good initial stability and also to provide a better seal to the initial osteotomy site.

Surface of the Crest Module

Machined and smooth collars were introduced for maintaining proper hygiene. The biological width of the implant including the sulcus depth is 3.08 mm while the bristles of a brush reach 0.5 to 1 mm of depth. This is the primary reason why a smooth surface is necessary to reduce plaque accumulation.¹⁷ However, the place-

ment of smooth surface of crest module at the crestal bone region leads to more marginal bone loss. This is because smooth collared implants placed in contact with crestal bone produces shear stresses leading to crestal bone loss. Furthermore, smooth collars may induce fibroblast growth which interrupts the contact between the bone and the implant creating a fibrous capsule instead.¹⁸ Herman et al conducted a study in 2001 to determine the suitable length and location of smooth collar to avoid crestal bone loss. In his study he placed transgingival implants in dogs. The implants were divided mainly into two study groups ; one group had roughened surface at the crestal bone region and the other group had a smooth collar of 1.5mm below the crestal bone region after which the roughened surface began. The two groups were observed for a period of 6 months in unloaded condition. In this study it was observed that within 1 month itself the group with a 1.5 mm smooth collar underwent marginal bone loss while no such bone loss was seen in the other group.¹⁹ Hanggi et al.²⁰ conducted similar experiments and the conclusion that can be raised from these experiments is that the smooth collar within the bone should be of minimum length possible.²⁰

The Body of the Implant

In the given literature it has been seen that implant body has influence on implant survival after loading of implants. Inappropriate body designs can cause early implant failure after loading. Early loading (within 1 week to 2 months after implant placement) cases, combined with softer bone types or shorter implants fall under the category most likely to fail.²¹ Goodacre et al conducted a review of literature between 1981 and 2003 according to which in soft bone type, loading causes a 16% increase in chances of failure.²² Weng et al,²³ conducted a study of 6 years and observed that 98% implants survived in the initial healing period. However, within 18 months of loading, implants of 7mm length failed 25% of the time.²³ The rate of failure was highest in short implants, specifically in the soft bone of the posterior maxilla, in early loading conditions.

The Size of the Implant

The implant body receives the biomechanical load from the prosthesis; this load is transferred to the surrounding hard tissue bone. This biomechanical load depends on two factors: the force being applied and the surface area throughout which that force is dissipated. The Surface Area over which the occlusal forces are dissipated play a major role in reducing the stresses between implant bone interface. $\text{Stress} = \text{Force} /$

Surface area thus it is evident that to reduce stress, the force must decrease or the surface area must increase. The size of an implant may be modified in either length or diameter.

The length of the Implant

The greater the length of the implant the more surface area it possesses to interact with the surrounding bone, thus an increased amount of stability can also be predicted. Under conditions such as lateral loading implant lengths greater than 15 mm in length have shown greater stability. Theoretically, increasing the implant length reduces the stresses of force transfer; however this only happens till a limit. Misch and Bidez¹⁴ placed cylindrical implants of different lengths in a computer bone model with ideal bone density and volume. According to the results of the analysis, implant lengths ranging from 10 – 15mm length have comparable force dissipation capability with implants of length 20 – 30mm. The highest stress region is the crestal bone region and regardless of the length of the implant the crestal region receives maximum stress. However the stress contours differ in softer bone types

where the stresses are directed more apically. Thus in softer bone types such as D3 and D4 bones, longer implants are beneficial.

The Width of the Implant

The width of the implant also increases the surface area of contact; this is a three dimensional volumetric increase in contact area. Brånemark et al. introduced a constant implant body diameter of 3.75 mm. Any implant body greater than 4 mm may be considered a "wide-diameter implant."

The wide-diameter implant may present surgical, loading, and prosthetic advantages. Osteotomy sites are made for a particular implant size during surgery, subsequently a proper drilling sequence is followed and an implant is placed with an initial torque known as insertion torque. The value of the insertion torque is an indicator of primary stability; a 30 – 40 Ncm value is mandatory for successful implant stability. However, even with proper protocol, at times the implant may not osseointegrate after the conventional healing period of 3 months. In this situation the surgical advantage of wide diameter implants can be seen. When regular body implant fails to integrate into the bone in the osteotomy site, the regular implant may be removed and replaced with the wide-body implant.

When it comes to primary stability, the increase in contact area of wide diameter does help the stability , however more important factors such as available bone dimensions should be kept in mind. For instance, a distance of 1.5 mm or greater should be kept between implant and tooth and a distance of 3mm or greater should be present between implant and another implant. Increasing the implant body might pose other problems such as unaesthetic appearance and stress shielding. Stress shielding phenomenon is seen when the force dissipation happens within the body of the implant without transference to the adjoining bone. This leads to disuse atrophy of the bone. Depending on the region of rehabilitation an ideal range of implant diameter has been considered. Mandibular incisors and maxillary lateral incisors: 3–3.5 mm diameter, Maxillary centrals, maxillary and mandibular canines and premolars: 4 mm diameter, Molars: 5–6 mm diameter.

Thread Shape

The thread primarily aids in mechanical retention as a result of increased surface area for osseointegration. Based on the cross-section of the thread, thread shape can be of five types : Square, V shaped, buttress, and reverse buttress types.²⁴ Changing the thread design in an implant can help change the angle of the load on the bone. Threaded implants convert occlusal loads into compressive, tension and shear stresses. In the square thread maximum load is converted to compressive stresses. In the V shaped, stresses are mostly converted into shear and tension stresses. The bone can withstand compressive forces better than shear and tensile forces and has more potential to resorb under the latter.²⁵

Kim et al²⁶ conducted a finite element analysis where he simulated implants with different thread shapes; the thread depth and number remaining constant. The square thread shape had least value of shear stresses as well as compressive stresses.²⁶ Chun et al conducted a similar study and came to the same conclusion.²⁷

The bone implant contact is also more in square thread shape. Steigenga et al.^{28,29} conducted a animal study where it was observed that when other parameters are kept the same, the thread shape with maximum bone implant contact and least reverse torque values. This makes the thread shape important in primary stability as well.^{28,29}

Thread Pitch

Defined as the distance from the centre of one thread to the centre of the adjacent thread measured parallel to the axis of a screw calculated by dividing unit length by the number of threads. The smaller or finer the pitch, the more threads on the implant body for a given unit length. This increases the surface area and decreases stress distribution per unit length of the implant body. It is considered as the most important design variable that affects the surface area of the implant. Roberts et al.³⁰ observed in an animal model that the thread number may affect the BIC percentage. When two different implant thread pitch designs were placed in the same animal, a higher BIC was observed with the implants with the greater thread number.³⁰

Thread Depth

The thread depth is defined as the distance from the tip of the thread to the body of the implant. It can also be defined as the distance between the major and minor diameter of the implant. Shallow threads tend to fracture more during insertion of the implant when compared to deeper threads.

Measurement of Implant Stability

Implant stability is the absence of clinical mobility immediately after insertion and after the integration of implant with bone. There are two types of stability primary implant stability and secondary stability. Primary stability refers to the mechanical seating of the implant; This type of stability signifies the engagement of the implant with the bone.

The latter refers to the biological stability achieved between bone and implant after the process of osseointegration has taken place.

- Torque levels can be evaluated during the insertion process with the help of a drilling unit especially designed for torque documentation or by use of manual torque wrenches. Both systems can measure torque levels during implant insertion. The higher the torque value the more firm the attachment of bone to implant. A minimum value of 40 Ncm, is required for immediate or early loading protocols. A value of 30 – 40 Ncm requires the conventional 4 – 6 months healing period before loading. However a value of greater than 50Ncm induces compressive stresses within the bone, which leads to vessel obstruction which can limit periimplant bone perfusion and induce bone necrosis.
- Insertion torque is a good way of measuring the stability of the implant during the placement of the implant, however the measurement of implant stability maybe required during the process of healing. This helps in assessing the loading protocol that can be followed and in judging the success of the implant integration process.
- Periotest and RFA methods are helpful in this; these versatile measuring techniques have made implant survival a much more predictable process. The Periotest device is electromagnetically controlled and essentially measures the micromotion created by the device. Given its mechanism it is clear that a lower value, indicating a lower level of micromotion, indicates better stability of implant.
- The newer magnetic RFA method - A special probe and sensor are used to assess a dental implant's resonance frequency. The probe is a transducer producing electromagnetic pulses and the sensor is a rod with magnet on top. The sensor is attached to the implant and the probe emits impulses; pulse duration is 1ms. The sensor will vibrate in response and the probe reads the frequency at which the sensor vibrates.

- The measurement unit for frequency is hertz, but when assessing implants, hertz are often converted into an implant stability quotient (ISQ). This value is mathematically derived from the frequency measurements, and ISQ was developed to create a scale of values, ranging from 1 to 100, that can be tracked and translated into micromobility and implant stability. High stability means >70 ISQ, between 60-69 is medium stability and < 60 ISQ is considered as low stability. If the initial ISQ value is high, a small drop in stability normally levels out with time.

Implant Stability In Grafted Site

Bone graft procedure is beneficial for increasing the stability of immediately placed implants, especially when the ISQ of implants is below ⁶⁵. A few factors need to be considered while placing bone grafts in immediate implant cases.

- Grafting is done in the buccal void between the implant and the socket wall, this partially preserves the dimensions of alveolar ridge after immediate implant placement.
- This procedure is more beneficial in the maxillary region where there is thin buccal bone.
- It is important to note that the initial primary stability will be given by the available bone itself. It is only after the healing process has taken place that the graft contributes to the stability of the implant.
- Also, if primary stability is achieved, a provisional restoration can be placed, since it may lead to midfacial soft tissue stability at immediate implants.
- Implant design features such as square threads and SLA surfaces should be considered for implant stability enhancement.

Implant Stability In Maxillary Sinus Lift Cases

The maxillary substantial augmentation procedure is a well established technique for increasing bone volume in the deficient posterior maxilla. Survival rates of single tooth replacements were found to be reduced if supported by implants < 10 mm in length. Survival rates of rough surfaced short implants for single-tooth replacement have been reported to approach those of implants ≥ 10 mm. However, this finding was predominantly obtained in the posterior mandible. For 10mm implant the minimum requirement is 12 mm of bone. This leaves 2mm of bone between the implant apex and the floor of the maxillary sinus. Less than 6mm of bone requires the lateral window approach for sinus floor elevation whereas more than 6mm of bone can be augmented by the transcresal approach of the sinus floor elevation. Less than 5mm bone will not provide the necessary primary stability for simultaneous implant placement. Loading protocol is also dictated by primary implant stability and is usually done within 8 – 12 months. Another consideration for implants to be placed in conjunction with SFE is the fact that bone density is often suboptimal in the posterior maxilla. It is therefore highly recommended to select an implant design whose geometry and surface characteristics can maximize primary stability. Although evidence is lacking to determine which geometric features are essential for maximum primary stability, a number of geometric designs have been proposed. These include threads with a modified shape, self-tapping threads, tapered profiles, and flared necks. On the other hand, there is strong evidence that the survival rate of implants with a roughened surface (96.9%) is significantly higher than the survival rate of implants with a machined surface (88%). However, since all implants with plasma sprayed, HA-coated, and sand-blasted/acid-etched surface types fall into the category of

"rough surface" implants, it is not clear how different surface treatments may affect implant survival and success. It has been suggested that healing periods before prosthetic loading can be reduced with micro-rough implants compared to implants with more traditional surface characteristics. Recently, implants offering a chemically modified and hydrophilic microrough surface have been developed (SLActive surface). In conjunction with SFE, there is no evidence of superiority to conventional surfaces at this time, although preclinical and clinical studies have yielded promising results for this newly developed surface type.

Implant Microgeometry

Implant surface condition or micro geometry has a more important role in initial bone healing as compared to macro geometry which has a role after loading of implant.³¹ The functional surface of the implant refers to that part of the implant that takes part in active force transmission of force. For example plasma spray coating increases the total surface area through bone implant contact by 600%. However the particles of plasma spray are as small as 8 microns and are too microscopic to transfer loads.^{32,33}

The enhancement of bone healing through the increase in surface roughness is because the roughened surface enhances adhesion of platelets, monocytes and osteoblasts. Hansson et al. 1999, proposed that the ideal surface of an implant should be covered with hemispherical pits approximately 1.5 micrometer in depth and 4 micrometer in diameter.³⁴ Histologic and Histomorphometric analysis was conducted by Watzek et al.³⁵ on machined and rough surface screw shaped and rough-surface cylinder implants after 18 months of occlusal loading in baboons. There BIC was significantly different, with screw-type implants having higher values in both the maxilla and mandible. The rough-surface screw had slightly more BIC than the machined surface screw. In addition, the trabecular bone pattern was irregular around the cylinder implants, but the bone was organized and perpendicular to the threads around the screw implants. Therefore, the bone trabeculae pattern and the higher BIC resulted in a superior support system for threaded implants.³⁵

Thus it can be inferred that, after occlusal loading the macro design takes precedence over the microdesign or surface condition. However, since surface characterization aids in healing of bone and thus it has role in secondary stability as well as primary stability.

Hydroxy Apatite Coated Implants

The inorganic material in human teeth is primarily composed of a calcium phosphate related to hydroxyapatite (HAP). The chemical composition and properties of HAP are comparable to those of the natural components of teeth. Because of its high biocompatibility, HAP has the potential to be used for many dental applications.

Further, due to its highly brittle nature, HAP alone cannot be used as an implant in load bearing uses. Uncoated metallic implants are also unsuitable due to a lack of biocompatibility with the local tissue environment. Thus, a coating of biocompatible materials such as HAP on metallic surfaces has become a promising field of dentistry. The coating of the surface of titanium dental implants with hydroxyapatite can improve the osseointegration of these devices because of the bioactivity of the molecule, which reduces the healing period and improves the bone fixation of the implant.

UV Light Activated Implants

One of the most crucial aspects of successful dental implant surgery is osseointegration of the jaw with the dental implant post. To achieve adequate osseointegration, the surface of the implant must be properly treated and sterilized before surgery. This is most commonly done via sandblasting and acid etching, which help clean the surface of the implant and prepare it for placement.

However, surface preparation treatments often make the surface material of the implant hydrophobic; thereby inhibiting successful osseointegration. This issue is resolved with a unique new UV activation technology, which studies show helps achieve 98% osseointegration within three months of dental implant surgery.

Conclusion

Implant design has been established as a crucial factor in implant survival. Implant design has been optimized and has evolved to include various features which increase their contact with the bone. This bone implant contact is essential for the stability of the implant, specifically primary stability. The implant design not only caters to the implant stability before loading but also has features to enhance stability after loading. After loading of the implant, the implant design is optimized to give favourable load transfer. This will prevent other complications such as screw loosening and marginal bone loss. These complications may lead to decrease in stability after loading. The product used by the implant team may increase or decrease the risk of screw loosening, crestal bone loss, marginal bone loss, peri-implantitis, esthetics of the soft tissue drape, implant failure, and implant body fracture. The decision of choosing the implant should be based on patient force factors. The bone density should be evaluated which will be a guiding factor in assessing the length and width of the implant to some extent. It is essential to measure the implant stability at various stages of the implant rehabilitation procedure. Methods to measure the same include many of which resonance frequency analysis is the most versatile. Implant stability quotient (ISQ) values obtained from RFA provides valuable information regarding the stability and the loading protocol. Grafting procedures done prior to implant placement increase the primary stability. Sometimes when immediate implant placement is done after extraction, grafting procedures become more complex, however these cases have to be thoroughly understood. A thorough knowledge of how implant design impacts the stability of the implant and its success is crucial. The decision is even more important when force factors are greater than usual, bone density is poorer than usual, or implant body size is reduced. This article provides a review which enhances the knowledge needed to select appropriate implant design, macro and micro geometry for optimum stability and success of implant.

References

1. Misch CE: Stress treatment theorem for implant dentistry. In Misch CE, editor: Contemporary implant dentistry, ed 3, St Louis, 2008, Elsevier Mosby, pg 68–91.
2. Misch CE: Prosthetic Options in Implant Dentistry editor: Contemporary implant dentistry, ed 2, ELSEVIER mosBY, pg 193
3. Misch CE: Force Factors Related to Patient Conditions (A Determinant for Implant Number and Size) editor: Contemporary implant dentistry, ed 2, ELSEVIER mosBY, pg 233
4. Misch CE: Force Factors Related to Patient Conditions (A Determinant for Implant Number and Size) editor: Contemporary implant dentistry, ed 2, ELSEVIER mosBY, pg 206

5. Misch CE, Misch CM: Generic terminology for endosseous implant prosthodontics, *J Prosthet Dent* 68: 809–812, 1992.
6. Misch CE, Misch CM: Generic terminology for endosseous implant prosthodontics, editor: Contemporary implant dentistry, ed 2, ELSEVIER mosBY, pg 29
7. Heimes, D., Becker, P., Pabst, A. *et al.* How does dental implant macrogeometry affect primary implant stability? A narrative review. *Int J Implant Dent* 9, 20 (2023)
8. Swami V, Vijayaraghavan V, Swami V. Current trends to measure implant stability. *J Indian Prosthodont Soc.* 2016 Apr-Jun;16 (2):124-30.
9. Monje A, Ravidà A, Wang HL, Helms JA, Brunski JB. Relationship Between Primary/Mechanical and Secondary/Biological Implant Stability. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 2019
10. Kohli, N., Stoddart, J.C. & van Arkel, R.J. The limit of tolerable micromotion for implant osseointegration: a systematic review. *Sci Rep* 11, 10797 (2021)
11. Bassir SH, El Kholy K, Chen CY, Lee KH, Intini G. Outcome of early dental implant placement versus other dental implant placement protocols: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Periodontol.* 2019 May; 90 (5): 493-506.
12. Dr. Nikhil N Pawar, Dr. Payal A Karkar. Loading protocol in implant dentistry: A review. *Int J Appl Dent Sci* 2020; 6 (3): 578-587.
13. Aparna IN, Dhanasekar B, Lingeshwar D, Gupta L. Implant crest module: a review of biomechanical considerations. *Indian J Dent Res.* 2012 Mar-Apr; 23 (2): 257-63.
14. Misch CE, Bidez. A scientific rationale for dental implant. In: Misch CE, editor. *Contemporary Implant Dentistry* 2 nd ed. St.Louis: Mosby; 1999.p. 329-43.
15. Shen WL, Chen CS, Hsu ML. Influence of implant collar design on stress and strain distribution in the crestal compact bone: A three-dimensional finite element analysis. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants* 2010; 25: 901-10.
16. Petrie CS, Williams JL. Comparative evaluation of implant designs: influence of diameter, length, and taper on strains in the alveolar crest. A three dimensional finite-element analysis. *Clin Oral Implants Res* 2005;16: 486-94.
17. Misch CE, Strong TD, Bidez MW. Scientific rationale for dental implant design. In: Misch CE, editor. *Contemporary Implant Dentistry* 3 rd ed. St.Louis: Mosby; 2008: pp 200-232
18. Misch CE. A scientific rationale for dental implant design. In: Misch CE, editor. *Dental Implant Prosthetics.* St.Louis: Mosby; 2005. p.322-48.
19. Hermann JS, Buser D, Schenk RK, Schoolfield JD, Cochran DL. Biologic Width around one-and two-piece titanium implants *Clin Oral Implants Res.* 2001;12: 559–71
20. Hänggi MP, Hänggi DC, Schoolfield JD, Meyer J, Cochran DL, Hermann JS. Crestal bone changes around titanium implants. Part I: A retrospective radiographic evaluation in humans comparing two non-submerged implant designs with different machined collar lengths *J Periodontol.* 2005;76: 791–802
21. Misch CE: Stress treatment theorem for implant dentistry. In Misch CE, editor: *Contemporary implant dentistry*, ed 3, St Louis, 2008, Elsevier Mosby, pg.348-350
22. Goodacre CJ, Bernal G, Runcharassaeng K, et al: Clinical complications with implants and implant prostheses, *J Prosthet Dent* 90:121, 2003.
23. Weng D, Jacobson Z, Tarnow D, et al: A prospective multi-center clinical trial of 3i machined surface implants: results after 6 years of follow-up, *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants* 18: 417–423, 2003.
24. Misch CE: Stress treatment theorem for implant dentistry. In Misch CE, editor: *Contemporary implant dentistry*, ed 3, St Louis, 2008, Elsevier Mosby, pg.360
25. Misch CE: Stress treatment theorem for implant dentistry. In Misch CE, editor: *Contemporary implant dentistry*, ed 3, St Louis, 2008, Elsevier Mosby, pg. 353 – 355
26. Kim WT, Cha YF, Oh SJ, et al: The three dimensional finite element analysis of stress according to implant thread design under the axial load, *Korean J Oral Surg* 27:3–8, 2001.
27. Chun HS, Cheong SY, Han JH, et al: Evaluation of design parameters of osseointegrated dental implants using finite element analysis, *J Oral Rehabil* 29: 565–574, 2002.
28. Steigenga JT: The effect of implant thread geometry on strength of osseointegration and the bone implant contact [master's thesis], Ann Arbor, MI, 2003, University of Michigan.
29. Steigenga J, Al-Shammari K, Misch CE, et al: Effects of implant thread geometry on percentage of osseointegration and resistance to reverse torque in the tibia of rabbits, *J Periodontol* 75:1233–1241, 2004
30. Roberts WE, Smith RK, Zilerman Y, et al: Osseous adaptation to continuous loading of rigid endosseous implants, *Am J Orthod* 86: 95–111, 1984.
31. Misch CE: Stress treatment theorem for implant dentistry. In Misch CE, editor: *Contemporary implant dentistry*, ed 3, St Louis, 2008, Elsevier Mosby, pg.349.
32. Lemons J: *Biomaterials in implant dentistry.* St Louis, 1993, Mosby.
33. Stefflik D, Corpe RS, Young TR, et al: Light microscopic and scanning electron microscopy retrieval analysis of implant biomaterials retrieved from humans and experimental animals, *J Oral Implantol* 27: 5–15, 2001.
34. Hansson S, Norton M. The relation between surface roughness and interfacial shear strength for bone anchored implants. A mathematical model. *J Biomech.* 1999
35. Watzek G, Zechner W, Ulm C, et al: Histologic and histomorphometric analysis of three types of dental implants following 18 months of occlusal loading: a preliminary study in baboons, *Clin Oral Implants Res* 16: 408–416, 2005.